

Omental Infarction Causing Left Lower Abdominal Pain

Tagalsir Alamin Logman*, Ahmed Dawoud, Basant Kumar sahuo , Tariq wahab

Department of General Surgery, Rustaq Hospital, Sultanate of Oman

Citation: Tagalsir Alamin Logman. Omental Infarction Causing Left Lower Abdominal Pain. *Int Case Rep Jour.* 2021;1(5):1.

Received Date: 09 December,2021; **Accepted Date:** 10 December,2021; **Published Date:** 12 December, 2021

***Corresponding author:** Tagalsir Alamin Logman, Department of General Surgery, Rustaq Hospital, Sultanate of Oman

Copyright: © Tagalsir Alamin Logman, Open Access 2021. This article, published in *Int Case Rep Jour (ICRJ)* (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

CLINICAL IMAGE

A 42 - year- old lady, presented with left lower abdomen of two weeks duration. Clinically she was tender at the left lower abdomen, otherwise her abdomen was soft. All her blood tests and emaging studies including CT were normal. She remained in pain after three days of observation and analgesics. She was taken for diagnostic laparoscopy and found to have a 3 × 3 cm omental piece at the left lower abdomen, medial to the sigmoid colon, twisted with narrow pedicle and infarcted. This was excised laparoscopically and the patient showed dramatic improvement post operatively and discharged home.

